

MESOSCALE CLIMATE MODELING ABOVE A METHANE LAKE ON TITAN

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Starting point: the mtWRF model

Research Paper

Air-sea interactions on titan: Lake evaporation, atmospheric circulation, and cloud formation

Scot C.R. Rafkin^{*}, Alejandro Soto

Icarus 2020

Implementation of a radiation scheme

Schneider et al 2012 (gray scheme)
Tomasko et al 2008 (Huygens/DISR)

The general solution does not change

Initial methane plume
(a few hours)

Beginning of the sea breeze
(~12h)

Extended sea breeze
(> 1 day)

contours = CH_4 mixing ratio (every 1 g/kg)
lake of 300 km at the center

Night [1-3 am]

NEW

Diurnal
evolution of
the sea
breeze

+

stronger
winds over
land at night

NEW

**Diurnal
evolution of
the sea
breeze**

**+
stronger
winds over
land at night**

Night [1-3 am]

Day [1-3 pm]

NEW Less cooling of the lake

with radiation ☀

without radiation

⇒ lake (and land) hotter (up to +3 K) + undergo diurnal variations (+/- 0.5 K)

NEW A different energy balance

with radiation ☀️

without radiation

$$\text{Bowen ratio} = \frac{\text{sensible heat}}{\text{latent heat}} \quad (\text{over the lake})$$

NEW A different energy balance

with radiation ☀

At equilibrium:

latent heat \approx sensible heat + solar + IR

\Rightarrow radiation matters!

$$\text{Bowen ratio} = \frac{\text{sensible heat}}{\text{latent heat}}$$

WHAT IF we add initial methane vapor? (1/3)

- ① modifications of the sea breeze: higher and less extended over land

0% initial humidity

80% initial humidity

WHAT IF we add initial methane vapor? (2/3)

② much higher lake temperatures

0% initial humidity

80% initial humidity

WHAT IF we add initial methane vapor? (3/3)

③ much less methane evaporation + with diurnal variations

0% initial humidity

80% initial humidity

Seasonal variations

1-3 am: 'night' →

max insolation
(huge day-night difference))

polar night
(only night)

1-3 pm: 'day' →

Summary: radiative transfer matters, we can't ignore it!

- Diurnal variations of the sea breeze:
 - extends over land at night
 - limited by strong convection cells during the day
- Change in the energy balance: we should not neglect solar and IR fluxes
 - same evaporation level
 - but less cooling of the lake
- Affected by initial humidity and seasons

Perspective: application to moist surfaces all over Titan
(in particular at Dragonfly landing site)